

***Barriers to and effective strategies for improving
Covid-19 service delivery to California farmworkers***

It is undeniable that California’s farmworkers are at an unusually high risk for being exposed to and acquiring COVID-19¹. This has been shown by carefully counting employment designations of Covid cases tabulated by local health departments at the time of taking the Covid test. In Monterey County, it was found that farmworkers were more than three times as likely to become infected by the virus than persons employed in the county’s Non-Agricultural industries.² Also, this becomes obvious if one looks at the rate of Covid cases per 100,000 by zip code. In Monterey County, for example, the top ten zip codes reported by the census as having the highest proportion of farmworkers are the same ten zip codes with the highest rates of Covid.³ (See chart below) Clearly, it is imperative to target this hard-to-reach group with Covid services.

Neighborhood	Percent Farmworkers	Rank of Cases per 100,000
San Ardo	54%	1
Chaular	54%	8
Southeast Salinas	50%	4
Greenfield	47%	2
King City	44%	3
San Lucas	40%	7
Gonzalez	37%	6
Soledad	29%	5
Castroville	27%	10
Northeast Salinas	19%	9

This presentation will first show why California farmworkers are so exposed to acquiring Covid and experience so many obstacles to receiving Covid-related services. I will base my findings on two surveys done in California. Then, I will present a very simple strategy for confronting the delivery problem based on Census data that could be provided to government and private groups that distribute the services.

¹ I will call COVID-19 just Covid throughout this paper.

² https://www.cirsinc.org/phocadownload/userupload/elevated_farmworker_vulnerability_covid-19_infection_research-report_abstract_final_villarejo_07-25-2020.pdf

³“COVID-19 among Farmworkers in America’s Salad Bowl: Measures of Covid-19 by geographic area”, Mines, R. and Ward, C. December, 2020

Our conclusion is a simple one. Government agencies and private front-line organizations would benefit in their service delivery planning by ranking first zip codes and then census tracts by levels of risk of Coronavirus for farmworkers. And, then the delivery of services like PPE, testing, contact tracking, promising therapies, vaccinations and public education to stem vaccination hesitancy could be targeted directly at these identified hot spots. Geography-guided targeting, in our view, if properly implemented could greatly help in getting sufficient resources to the farmworkers most at risk.

But first, who are California Farmworkers?

For this part, I took data about farmworkers myself from the DOL's California National Agricultural Workers Survey (NAWS) 2014-2016 public use tape.

1. First, it should be remembered that even today many farmworkers are unaccompanied, relatively young men, mostly from Mexico. These farmworkers are more than a third of the total and are unaccompanied by spouse, children or parents ⁴

These young men typically live in crowded subleased rooms in apartments or small houses, three or four to a room. The roommates are often from different social networks and go to different work destinations so they are constantly exposed to infection from people beyond their roommates.

These young men without wives or mothers nearby tend not to be in contact with any institutions of health or education. According to the NAWS data, most of the unaccompanied men haven't seen a doctor or nurse in the 2 years before the interview.

2. Among the other 2/3rds of the other "accompanied" farmworkers, the average age is 41.
3. Of these accompanied farmworkers, 86% are married and 80% have children living with them.
4. Most of these children are U.S- born citizens
5. But, the crowding occurs among the families as well. In a study done in Salinas, CA in 2017, 54% of the residences had multiple households living at the same address. And, about ½ of these were not multigenerational but unrelated residents living together to save rent.⁵ So, like the unaccompanied men, people from different social networks are working and socializing separately but yet sharing the same kitchens and bathrooms. It is typical for two and even three farmworker families to share a two-bedroom house or apartment.

⁴ 72% less than 40 and 87% are men in the 2014-2016 NAWS data.

⁵ <https://rickmines.files.wordpress.com/2021/01/salinas-housing-2017.pdf>

6. There is a mixture of living locations, but probably about half live in small towns and half live in farmworker neighborhoods in urban areas like Fresno located in agricultural counties.
7. About 3 in 5 are undocumented and 90% are Latino immigrants, almost all of which are Mexicans.
8. About half work for farm labor contractors rather than being directly hired by growers. Often the worker only knows his crew boss and never sees the higher levels of management.
9. About 23% are over 50; they are not that a young population. And, many have co-morbidities. (see Chart below)

10. The median education is 8 years of school.
11. Many, we estimate 16%, of California farmworkers are speakers of indigenous American languages with very different habits and customs. There will be added obstacles for this population.⁶

In sum, there are still lots of unaccompanied young men, but also even more young families with US-born children. About 700,000 farmworkers not counting their family members work in CA. Most, only have a basic education, most are poor, few speak English.

Now I'm going to tell you about another survey done last summer that describes how California farmworkers are adapting to the pandemic.

In 2020, the California Institute of Rural Studies did the Covid Survey of 915 farmworkers all over rural CA in 2020.⁷

The farmworkers reported in that survey that:

⁶ <http://www.indigenousfarmworkers.org/>

⁷ <http://covid19farmworkerstudy.org/>

- Only just over half of the employers provided masks to their workers.
- One in five reported that their boss required them to work less than 6 feet apart.
- Only one in five of the workers said that they were shown how to use PPE.
- One half traveled to work with a stranger not from their household
- About half said that their hours were cut back due to Covid. Most said that they had added trouble paying their bills due to Covid.
- About 3 in 10 said they wouldn't seek health care due to fear of the government or fear of what might happen at a clinic

In sum, the demographic profile and the living and working conditions of farmworkers is an invitation to acquire the virus and an obstacle to receive services for the virus.

Getting resources to the California farmworkers:

Farmworkers can theoretically be accessed either at work or at home. Both should be done but getting services to them at work in my view is insufficient for two reasons.

1. This will only be possible with employer cooperation and that will not be universal.
2. According to the literature, most of the spread happens in their neighborhoods and traveling to work and not at work.⁸ Again, they live in crowded housing often with nonrelative co-residents from other social circles. So, they are sharing bathrooms and kitchens with people from other social networks. As stated above, they travel to work with strangers. And, the work sites are outside and usually enforce some precautions against spread at work like masking, distancing and hygiene.⁹

So, here is what we propose:¹⁰

First, we identify the zip codes in one county at a time by their Covid-19 cumulative incidence numbers. In California, these are available (or should be available) from the County Public Health Departments.

Next, we gather basic data about each zip code from the American Community Survey (ACS) at the zip code level. This is extraordinarily easy.¹¹ The ACS just lays out the various variables in 5-year summaries for the reader for every zip code in the nation. So, one can organize the demographic variables within each zip codes by the county really quite readily.

One can also choose poorer zip codes from other reliable data sources like the Healthy Places Index or HPI in California. The HPI classifies zip codes by poverty measures but these are not

⁸ <https://science.sciencemag.org/content/370/6515/406>

⁹ See COFS data for hygiene, mask wearing and distancing.

¹⁰ Statistician colleague Coburn Ward, Professor emeritus from UOP did the statistics for the paper.

¹¹ See: <https://www.census.gov/acs/www/data/data-tables-and-tools/narrative-profiles/>.

correlated with cases of COVID and are not customized for farmworkers. It is not that difficult to customize the identification of where farmworker at risk live first by the zip code and then by extension down to the census tract level as we will explain below.

My statistical partner Coburn Ward and myself did a practice run on 2 counties in California and I will show you briefly our results so that you can understand what the method is I'm proposing. The two counties are two of the leading agricultural ones in California but they are quite different and so show us some of the challenges we will face in the different regions of the state. We have not applied this technique to other counties.

I'll go through each county separately so you can appreciate how identification of where to target resources will vary from county to county. Let's start with Monterey County. Here the separate zip codes for farmworkers is quite stark. Those of you who have vacationed in the Monterey area know that nearly all the agriculture in the County, the salad bowl of America, is located in an interior valley called Salinas. In that valley almost all the approximately 80,000 farmworkers and their families live. On the coast, in towns like Pebble Beach and Carmel-by-the-Sea, there are very few farmworkers. This fact simplifies the analysis because, as you probably already have guessed, most of the Covid cases are in the interior valley area where the farmworkers reside.

The first task is to determine what are the most significant variables in the county for Covid. Or, put another way, which variables correlate by zip code with the cumulative incidences of Covid per 100,000 residences for the county. Just using the percent of agricultural employment is insufficient since the American Community Survey data is not 100% reliable and by using a few highly correlated variables along with agriculture strengthens the correlation with Covid cases per 100,000.

We checked the correlation of various variables we judged to be correlated with the presence of farm workers such as: proportion of agricultural employment, proportion of no high school diploma, proportion of poverty, proportion who speak Spanish, proportion of foreign born, proportion of non-citizens, household size, and others with the Covid rate per 100,000 for each zip code. (see list below)

- **Proportion Agric Employment**
- **No High School Diploma**
- **Percent in Poverty**
- **Proportion Foreign Born**
- **Proportion who speak Spanish**
- **Proportion foreign born**
- **Proportion non-citizens**
- **Household size**
- **Etc.**

For the county of Monterey, we tested many of these variables. And, we discovered that the best fit was for these four: No high school diploma, proportion foreign born, proportion agriculturally employed and proportion in poverty.

Now, for the very small zip codes, it is not necessary to break down the neighborhoods more to increase the accuracy of targeting. For example, San Ardo has 806 residents. But, for many of the larger zip codes more precision is necessary. Zip codes frequently have 60,000 or more residents.

And, unfortunately, Covid cases are not available to the county health departments down to the census tract level. So, we had to be creative. Therefore, we made the following assumption: The variables that are correlated with the Covid cases per 100,000 at the zip code level are also correlated with Covid cases at the census tract level of which these zip codes are composed. Or said differently, in a given county, Covid is correlated with certain variables, so we are assuming that the same variables will be predictors of Covid at the subsets of these zip codes, namely at the level of the census tracts.

Now, I don't expect you to see the numbers on this table below clearly. But what we did is find a linear combination of these four variables that are very highly correlated with Covid cases per 1000 at the zip code level. We applied this linear formula to each census tract and used the resulting scores to rank the census tracts for farmworkers.

4. Zip Code	Neighborhood	Census Tract	No High School Diploma over 25	Proportion Foreign Born	Proportion Agric Employment	Proportion in Poverty	Ranked by Farmworker Score
93905	SE Salinas	7.01	72%	82%	58%	28%	1
93905	SE Salinas	7.02	71%	86%	59%	24%	2
93905	SE Salinas	6	74%	81%	47%	28%	3
93905	SE Salinas	9	63%	74%	47%	38%	4
93905	SE Salinas	5.01	66%	85%	55%	22%	5
93905	SE Salinas	8	69%	79%	49%	24%	6
93905	SE Salinas	106.07	64%	79%	50%	22%	7
93905	SE Salinas	5.02	53%	61%	34%	19%	8
93905	SE Salinas	106.05	53%	71%	23%	13%	9
93906	NE Salinas	2	48%	59%	24%	17%	10
93906	NE Salinas	105.06	53%	68%	19%	16%	11
93905	SE Salinas	106.08	60%	72%	11%	11%	12
93906	NE Salinas	2	48%	59%	11%	17%	13
93906	NE Salinas	4	33%	51%	19%	22%	14
93905	NE Salinas	106.04	39%	62%	25%	7%	15
93906	NE Salinas	105.05	39%	57%	19%	10%	16
93906	NE Salinas	1.03	34%	47%	8%	20%	17
93906	NE Salinas	3	36%	47%	11%	10%	18
93906	NE Salinas	1.01	30%	28%	11%	6%	19
93906	NE Salinas	106.03	18%	42%	8%	6%	20
93906	NE Salinas	1.04	19%	37%	4%	7%	21

You see in Table above that the highest ranked census tracts are all found in Southeast Salinas which have the highest concentration of farmworkers. These 9 census tracts have rates of employment in agriculture between 23% and 58%. Only census tract 106.08 from the Southeast ranks lower on the scale than one tract (105.06) from the Northeast. If one has limited resources to target tests, vaccines, contact tracing or other resources to these neighborhoods, this ranking should aid in knowing where to begin delivering services. After all, it is easy to provide maps to outreach workers of census tracts.

Now, let's turn to Fresno County for another example and a further explanation of our method.

In Fresno county again we tested the various variables that we showed you above that we feel are most likely to be correlated with the rate of Covid per 100,000 and where farmworkers reside.

We again created a correlation matrix which shows the correlation of each variable with every other one to test the importance of the various variables relative to each other. One can see in the table below the correlation of each variable with the COVID-19 cases per 100,000 residents for the 46 zip codes with available data in Fresno. They all register high correlations. The most significant associations with COVID-19 are for the proportion that speak Spanish (proxy for poor immigrants) and the household size (proxy for crowdedness). But, the other 4 are also strongly associated with the number of cases per 100,000.

Correlation of Cases per 100,000 with Six Variables

Var. 1	Var. 2	Var. 3	Var. 4	Var. 5	Var. 6
Household Size	% Non-naturalized Foreign Born	% over 25 who Speak Spanish	% over 25 No finish of High School	% of Private Employment in Agriculture	% in Poverty
0.744	0.718	0.793	0.701	0.522	0.716

We then ran a linear regression using all 6 variables to find a prediction formula for the cases per 100,000. One by one, insignificant variables were removed from the regression. The final trimmed regression model only contained the variables (above #3) "speak Spanish" and (above #5) "private employment in agriculture".

Next, we ranked the regression's predicted cases. Stated differently, we ordered the zip codes 1 to 46 according to their likelihood to have COVID cases based on these 2 variables. We subsequently ranked zip codes by actual cases. In this way, each zip code was ranked 1 to 46 in two different ways with 1 the highest case (or predicted case) rate. The plot below gives a picture of the correspondence of the two ranking systems. The correlation of the rankings of the 46 zip codes ordered by COVID-19 cases per 100,000 against our new ranking based on the association of COVID-19 cases with our 2 variables is now 0.869.

It should be noted that a high proportion of farmworkers live in urban areas in Fresno (and most other counties) with multiple census tracts per zip code. We made a calculation based on the total population in the zip code and the proportion of employment in the zip code based on the American Community Survey and found that 36% of the farmworkers live in the city of Fresno or Clovis. And, at least another 15% live in cities like Selma, Reedley and Sanger that are larger than 20,000 in population which have multiple census tracts.

This is not a complicated statistical challenge to do this for all the farmworker counties in California from which all the census tracts can be ranked allowing for the targeting of the ones where the virus is most likely to have the most accumulated incidences.

The same data can be derived easily for any census tract in the United States. And, a ranking of the census tracts by likelihood of risk can be made. The service delivery can be targeted according to this census-tract ranking developed by the method we suggest.

Once the census tracts and small zip codes are chosen, the front-line groups will, of course, need to identify the pharmacies, schools, community centers, home-town clubs, sports events, laundromats, flea markets, churches and other places suitable for distributing the service needed by the community. When dealing with difficult-to-reach groups, the familiarity with the culture, languages and habits of the population are crucial for successful outreach. And, it is crucial to understand that if farmworkers are going to be reached with services during this tragic period, a huge investment in resources for outreach will be necessary. We hope that knowing precisely which neighborhoods to outreach to will be helpful. But, without an enormous publicly and philanthropically funded effort at outreach the farmworkers will be ignored.

